

Hetero β -Diketone C³-Bonded Platinum(II) Complexes

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Reaction of [Pt(ac.ac) (C³-ac.ac) (Py)] with Hbfac, Htfac, [Pd(hfac) (bpy)] hfac, Pd(hfac)₂ and Pd(tfac)₂ gave complexes of the type [Pt(ac.ac) (C³-X) (py)], (X=hfac, tfac). The complexes were characterised on the basis of analysis, infrared and ¹H nmr data.

KETONIC coordination of oxygen of the C³-carbon bonded acetylacetonate moiety in the ionic complex K[Pt(ac.ac)(C³-ac.ac)Cl] have been well studied^{1,2}. Reaction of the neutral complex [Pt(ac.ac)(C³-ac.ac)(py)] (I) with copper and nickel halides and palladium complexes was being studied by us.

The complex [Pt(ac.ac) (C³-ac.ac)Py] (I) contains two ketonic oxygen atoms and these can coordinate to another metal ion or can form chelate with the metal if hydrogen at the central carbon atom can be abstracted by a base. On reacting complex I with metal halides (Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}) in alcoholic medium, the cleavage of the Pt-C bond by electrophilic attack was observed. But on reaction with [Pd(hfac)(py)]hfac and Pd(hfac)₂ complexes the main product was the Pt^{II} complexes

[Pt(ac.ac) (C³-X)Py], (X=hfac, tfac) containing the chelated acetylacetonate and the C³-carbon bonded hfac implying the lability of the C³-carbon bonded moiety. Reaction of I with hexafluoroacetylacetonate (hfac) and trifluoroacetylacetonate (tfac) also produced the same type of hetero β -diketone complexes.

Experimental

I (0.25 g) was dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ (5 ml) and [Pd(hfac) (bpy)] hfac (0.36 g) or Pd(hfac)₂ (0.276 g) or Pd(tfac)₂ (0.218 g) was dissolved in 5 ml acetone. Both the solutions were mixed and stirred at room temperature for 6 h. Volume of the resulting solution was concentrated to 5 ml and after adding hexane (10 ml) the solution was kept in freeze for 5 h. The yellow precipitate that separated was filtered and treated several times with hexane and dried *in vacuo*, [Pt(ac.ac)(C³-hfac) (py)] (Found : C, 31.54 ; H, 2.51 ; N, 2.62. Calcd. C, 31.03 ; H, 2.24 ; N, 2.41%) ; [Pt(ac.ac) (C³-tfac) (py)] (Found: C, 33.88 ; H, 2.75 ; N, 2.42. Calcd. C, 34.2 ; H, 3.04 ; N, 2.66%). The complexes were also obtained by refluxing compound I (0.2 g) in CH₂Cl₂ (3 ml) with hfac or tfac (1 ml) and toluene (10 ml) for 4 h followed by the similar work up.

TABLE I—INFRARED SPECTRA (cm⁻¹)

Compd.	$\nu_{C=O}$		Py ring vib.	ν_{Pt-C}	ν_{Pt-O}	ν_{Pt-N}
	C-bonded β -dik.	O-bonded β -dik.				
Pt(ac.ac)(C ³ -hfac)(py)	1735	1583	1613	566	467	332
	1693	1560				
Pt(ac.ac)(C ³ -tfac)(py)		1527	1613	570	465	333
	1728	1586				
	1668	1563				
		1532		540		
	¹ H nmr spectra δ (ppm)					
	O-bonded β -dik.	C-bonded β -dik.		Py		
Pt(ac.ac)(C ³ -hfac)(py)						
CH ₃	1.84 s	—		—		
CH	1.92 s	5.8 ss		7.4		
	5.48 s			8.2		
				8.4		
Pt(ac.ac)(C ³ -tfac)(py)						
CH ₃	1.8 s	2.3 ss				
CH	1.88 s	5.32 ss		7.8		
	5.08 s			8.1		
				8.4		

Infrared spectra (nujol) were measured using Jasco and Hitachi spectrophotometers. ¹H nmr spectra were measured in CD₂Cl₂ solutions using TMS as the internal reference by Jeol JNM 100 MHz spectrometer.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of analysis the complexes have the composition [Pt(ac.ac)(X)(py)], (X = hfac, tfac). Infrared spectra of the complexes reveal two types of carbonyl stretching frequencies. The higher carbonyl stretching frequencies are assigned to the central carbon bonded hfac or tfac while the lower ones to ac.ac (Table I). The complexes also exhibit Pt-C, Pt-O and Pt-N stretching modes in the far-infrared region³. ¹H nmr spectra of the above complexes show the methine proton signal around 6 ppm (Table I) as expected⁴.

The experimental results indicate that the C³-

carbon bonded acetylacetonate moiety in complex I is quite labile and is exchanged with the C³-carbon bonded hexafluoroacetylacetonate⁵. However, the reaction of [Pd(ac.ac)(C³-ac.ac)(py)] with [Pd(bpy)(hfac)]hfac results in the formation of complex of the type [Pd(bpy)(ac.ac)]hfac⁶ probably due to the cleavage of the Pd-C bond of the central carbon bonded acetylacetonate by the attack of hfac anion.

References

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